

NONVERBAL COMPONENT OF AN INTERNET MEME

Safayeva Mamura Oqil kizi

The National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek
teacher of Translation theory and comparative linguistics

e-mail: mamuraakilova@gmail.com

Annotation: This article is devoted to nonverbal features of internet memes. Memes reflect cultural stereotypes and phenomena of modern reality, which are relevant and interesting for Internet users. An adequate interpretation of Internet memes requires a coincidence of the components of the cultural baggage of the participants in communication, a community of relevant presuppositions. In this paper, meaning of colors in internet memes are analyzed. They are illustrated with examples.

Key words: internet meme, picture, pragmatics, background, colors, effect, reader, pattern.

The nonverbal component of a meme serves several important functions. On the one hand, it is of great importance in terms of content, because it helps to reveal the idea lay down by the author, which is often unclear from the accompanying inscription.

On the other hand, it performs an important function of attracting attention, because it is the non-verbal component that first of all catches the eye in a meme. For this purpose, the authors use all the possibilities of graphic design: color design, Photoshop, various fonts, frames, etc.

The image in a meme is usually a picture, drawing, photograph, or still from a movie. Regardless of the variety, it must have a strong pragmatic effect to convey the author's main idea. The image can be either believable, authentic, visual, or, conversely, shocking, absurd and grotesque. You can often find shocking or fantastic pictures and photographs in Internet memes.

In order to make a meme bright and attractive, the authors pay attention not only to the image in the meme, but also to auxiliary visual aids: color, font, background, frame. Let's take a closer look at these auxiliary tools.

The color used in an Internet meme is an important component of the visual component of the meme. In addition to the aesthetic function that color performs in a meme, giving brightness, saturation, harmony or contrast, color can also serve as a means of creating a certain atmosphere or a certain mood, because a number of psychological studies have scientifically proven the emotional impact of color on a person³.

³ Яньшин П. В. Цвет как фактор психической регуляции // Прикладная психология. – 2000. – № 4. – Р. 14-27.

Red is a passionate, exciting, active color. Promotes increased anxiety and hostile mood. Increases anxiety and encourages activity. Associated with heat, fire, blood.

Orange color has an inspiring effect. Stimulates the nervous system, improves mood. Associated with a cheerful and cheerful mood.

Yellow color is a mental stimulant. It is characterized by activity and radiance. It lifts the mood, attracts attention and inspires.

Green color has a hypnotic and calming effect. Associated with peace and serenity. It has a beneficial effect on a person in states of anxiety, fear and restlessness.

Blue color has a sedative and inhibitory effect. Associated with coldness, thoughtfulness, sadness, despondency. Gives peace and relieves pain.

Gray is an inert and expressionless color, associated with lethargy and passivity. Doesn't encourage action. Capable of creating a negative impression.

White is a sublime and pure color. Associated with sincerity and coolness. Stimulates mental activity, encourages activity.

The color **black** has a very strong influence on a person's emotional state. Promotes an increase in emotional stress, depression and anxiety. Associated with emptiness, death and darkness.

Obviously, the authors of Internet memes use color as a tool for creating the emotional atmosphere in the meme. For example, by using the color yellow in a meme, authors can enhance the effect of the joke used in the meme because yellow has an optimistic impulse. At the same time, a meme with a predominance of blue color may convey a difficult emotional state, characterized by anxiety or melancholy.

Let's consider a number of memes with a characteristic color design, where color, having an emotional impact on a person, is an important means of creating an image.

1) In the Internet meme in Figure 82, the color red creates a tense and hostile

atmosphere. It conveys feelings of anger and irritability. The angry expression on the man's face in the meme looks even more terrifying against the red background. It should be noted that the man's tie is also partially red, adding to the tense effect. This creates a comic effect: the intensity of the emotional experience of a man who laments, "Back in my day, Adam Sandler movies were funny," makes the viewer laugh because the overly angry reaction seems unjustified.

Figure 82

2) In the Internet meme in Fig. 83 black color is a means of creating a gloomy and depressive mood. The black color enhances the effect of the sad inscription and creates a gloomy and painful atmosphere.

Figure 83

Figure 84

3) This meme (Fig. 84) has a comic effect. A joke is played that makes fun of people who complain of depression. The joke can be translated into Russian like this: “Breaking into a doctor’s office because of pain. The diagnosis is depression.” Shades of blue create a depressing, overwhelming effect, conveying a depressive, sad state. In addition, there is a play on words: the word break down, which is used in the direct meaning of “break in,” also has the meaning of “psychological breakdown.” The play on words enhances the pragmatic effect of the meme.

4) In this meme (Fig. 85), an atmosphere of fun and cheerfulness is formed thanks to the verbal component, which is reinforced by the color yellow. Yellow color, being a mental stimulant, gives the meme dynamism and optimism and creates a light and cheerful mood.

Figure 85

Figure 86

5) In the Internet meme in Figure 86, which shows the quote, the color green creates an atmosphere of thoughtfulness, deep mental contemplation, and meditation. Due to its characteristics, the color green brings a touch of philosophy to this meme.

6) This meme (Fig. 87), designed in white, creates a sublime atmosphere and helps convey the purity and sincerity of maternal love. In this case, the white color attracts

attention to the meme, creates a contrast with the black inscription, and thereby contributes to the accentuation of the inscription in the meme, i.e. makes the reader think about the inscription. In addition, the Internet meme is an imitation of a handwritten note.

You're beautiful.
Don't you forget that.
Love, mommy
miseryslife.tumblr.com

Figure 87

Figure 88

7) The Internet meme in Figure 88 uses the color gray, which creates a melancholy and inert image. The gray color mutes the picture and makes you pay attention to the touching inscription. The gray color brings a sad mood to the meme.

In conclusion, we can say that color is an important tool for creating an image and emotional atmosphere and performs a certain pragmatic function, influencing the viewer.

Consider the role of font in a meme. As a rule, the Arial font is used in memes because, firstly, it is one of the most common fonts on the Internet, and the degree of recognition of the font is one of the factors that guarantees the readability and understanding of the text⁴. Secondly, it does not have patterns or decoration and therefore does not distract attention from the content of the verbal component of the meme.

However, to achieve imagery, authors can resort to other fonts, because the font has imaginative potential. For example, the Internet meme in Figure 89 uses a handwritten font, which, through its allusion to personal letters, creates an atmosphere of intimate, intimate conversation. “The author seems to lean in to talk to the reader personally, this is an attempt to convey friendliness and close relationships⁵.”

⁴ Морозова Л. В., Мурын И. Н. Психофизиологическая специфика восприятия печатного шрифта // Вестник Северного (Арктического) федерального университета. Серия: Естественные науки. – 2013. – № 3. – Р. 76-84.

⁵ Прохоров А. В. Процесс инференции в понимании рекламного текста // Социально-экономические явления и процессы. – 2011. – №8. – Р.225-228.

Figure 89

Figure 90

And the meme below (Fig. 90) uses a gothic font, which helps create a dark, sinister atmosphere and creates some involvement in the Middle Ages, initiating an allusion to dark forces.

So, we can say that a font, in addition to fulfilling its main function of providing ease of perception of information, can act as a means of creating imagery and a special atmosphere, indicating the time, circumstances, and authorship of the text.

Sometimes meme authors resort to such auxiliary means as a frame and background. Here you need to pay attention to the famous demotivators, which have a standard design: a picture with an accompanying inscription on a black background. Apparently, the black background was not chosen by chance; it allows you to focus attention on the content of the meme. The demotivator sets in advance the “rules” for the perception of information, as if warning the reader about the “danger”: the meme will contain a joke, paradox, dissonance, riddle and other cognitively complicated situations.

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